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Scaling autonomous logistics

D3.5 Public architecture design report

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Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	11
2. Introduction	12
2.1. Purpose & scope	12
2.2. Confidentiality	12
2.3. Related documents	12
2.4. Applicability and target platforms	13
2.5. Model Based-Design approach	13
3. Designing with Capella tool	15
3.1. Design concepts	15
3.1.1. Logical Architecture	15
3.1.2. Logical Component (LC)	15
3.1.3. Logical Function (LF)	16
3.1.4. Functional Exchange (FE)	16
3.1.5. Diagram (LAB)	17
3.1. Physical design concepts	17
3.1.1. Physical Architecture	17
3.1.2. Physical Component (PC)	17
3.1.3. Physical Link	17
3.2. Co-design with functional requirements	18
3.3. AWARD Design context	19
3.3.1. AWARD AGTS	19
3.3.2. AWARD ADV	20
4. AWARD ADS design	23
4.1. ADS-Sense	23
4.1.1. Role	23
4.1.2. Data flow	24
4.1.3. Functions details	25
4.2. ADS-Plan	28
4.2.1. Role	28
4.2.2. Data flow	29
4.2.3. Functions details	29
4.3. ADS-Act	34
4.3.1. Role	34
4.3.2. Data flow	34
4.3.3. Functions details	35
4.4. ADS-Monitor	36
4.4.1. Role	36

4.4.2.	Data flow	37
4.4.3.	Functions details	37
4.5.	System integrity errors	40
4.5.1.	Role	40
4.5.2.	Functional explanation	40
5.	Sensors & ADS integration	43
5.1.	Testing vehicle (ADV).....	43
5.2.	Sensors (Inputs for ADS-Sense).....	43
5.2.1.	Radars	43
5.2.2.	Cameras	46
5.2.3.	EasyMile lidar based system	48
5.2.4.	Other sensors.....	50
5.3.	Accessories of the considered test platform (ADV platform)	50
6.	Cyber security.....	52
6.1.	Purpose	52
6.2.	Standards and Best Practices	52
6.3.	Automated Vehicle (AV)	52
6.3.1.	Overall cybersecurity management	52
6.3.2.	Physical Entry Points	52
6.3.3.	Internet connectivity	52
6.3.4.	GPS / Localization	53
6.3.5.	Obstacle detection.....	53
6.3.6.	Network	53
6.3.7.	Sensors.....	53
6.3.8.	AWARD ADS solution.....	53
6.3.9.	Platform control.....	54
7.	Conclusion	55
8.	Annex.....	56
8.1.	ADV connectivity	56
8.2.	ADV electrical view	56

List of figures

Figure 1: Relationships and dependencies between the different AWARD deliverables	12
Figure 2: AWARD autonomous driving vehicle platforms.....	13
Figure 3: Logical Component illustration	15
Figure 4: Logical Function illustration	16
Figure 5: Independent Logical Function illustration	16
Figure 6: Functional Exchange illustration.....	17
Figure 7: Logical Component illustration	17
Figure 8: Physical Link illustration.....	17
Figure 9: Requirement illustration	18
Figure 10: Requirement attributes illustration	18
Figure 11: Requirement allocation to LF illustration	18
Figure 12: Logical architecture view of ADS in context of AGTS	19
Figure 13: Structure view of ADS in context of AGTS	21
Figure 14: AWARD ADS in context of ADV	22
Figure 15: AWARD ADS and its identified main functions	23
Figure 16: Functions involving mainly ADS-Sense	23
Figure 17: I/O of ADS-Sense	24
Figure 18: Provide consolidated localization diagram.....	25
Figure 19: Localization map.....	26
Figure 20: Sensor's LFs involved in perception function	27
Figure 21: Provide sensors operational status diagram.....	28
Figure 22: Functions involving mainly ADS-Plan	28
Figure 23: I/O of ADS-Plan	29
Figure 24: AWARD Collision Avoidance	30
Figure 25: Semantic map used for prediction	31
Figure 26: AWARD trajectory following	32
Figure 27: Crossing intersections with traffic lights	33
Figure 28: Semantic traffic light element on path.....	33
Figure 29: Functions involving mainly ADS-Act.....	34
Figure 30: I/O of ADS-Act	34
Figure 31: AWARD Interacting with road users	36
Figure 32: Functions involving mainly ADS-Monitor	36
Figure 33: I/O of ADS-Monitor.....	37
Figure 34: Monitoring for collision avoidance	37
Figure 35: Monitoring for trajectory deviation	38
Figure 36: Monitoring for traffic light intersections	38
Figure 37: Consolidate AV status and errors.....	40
Figure 38: Provide sensors operational status.....	41
Figure 39: Provide platform status.....	42
Figure 40: Baggage tractor outdoor by day and by night.....	43
Figure 41: Accessories.....	50
Figure 42: ADV connection functions.....	56
Figure 43: ADV physical view	58

List of tables

Table 1: Allocated requirements to safety functions	39
Table 2: Navtech radar datasheet details	43
Table 3: Roof radar usage and position	44
Table 4: Radars belt datasheet details.....	44
Table 5: Vehicle belt radar usage and position	45
Table 6: Adasky viper camera datasheet details.....	46
Table 7: Front viper camera usage and position	46
Table 8: Foresight camera datasheet details	46
Table 9: Front vision camera usage and position	47
Table 10: Ottopia camera datasheet details.....	47
Table 11: Ottopia camera usage and position.....	47
Table 12: Lidar characteristics	48
Table 13: Lidars usage and position	49
Table 14: Embedded IMU model	50
Table 15: Embedded GNSS modem model	50
Table 16: Physical and Logical allocation (Figure 43)	57

List of acronyms

ADS	Automated Driving System
ADV	Autonomous Driving Vehicle
AGTS	Automated ground Goods Transportation System
AV	Automated Vehicle
CAN	Controller Area Network
ECA	Emergency Collision Avoidance
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HDV	Heavy-Duty Vehicles
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IP	Ingress Protection
IPSec	Internet Protocol Secured
LAB	Logical Architecture Blank
LOFM	Logistics Operations and Fleet Management
NEMA	National Electrical Manufacturers Association
OBU	On Board Unit
ODD	Operational Design Domain
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
RSU	Road Side Unit
SI	Supporting Infrastructure
SLS	Supporting Logistic Systems
TLS	Transport Layer Security
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything

Glossary

CAN	A Controller Area Network is a standard vehicle bus used to enable communication between automotive ECUs.
LAB	A Logical Architecture Blank is a diagram used in Capella to describe functional exchanges between logical components owning logical functions. Beyond the data exchange between logical functions, the advantage of this diagram is to know through which logical component data is exchanged.
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System is a mechanism aiming to obtain its proper position thanks to reception of a signal coming from at least four satellites. The GNSS receiver measures the transmitting time of satellite signals and computes its position according to reception time of signals.
IP	Ingress Protection code represents the degree of protection ensured by a electrical enclosures against intrusion, dust, accidental contact and water.
IPSec	Internet Protocol Secure is a group of protocols used as a tunnel where transit some data. This tunnel enables to have confidentiality on these data and acts like virtual wire secured between two programmable computers.
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic is a process used for correcting positioning errors from GNSS positioning calculation.
System of Systems	A "System of Systems" (SoS) is a SOI whose elements are managerially and/or operationally independent systems.
TLS	A Transport Layer Security is a protocol involved in cyber security to provide encryption during network transmission.

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable “D3.5 – Architecture design” initiates a technical design approach of the AWARD autonomous driving system. It is the first deliverable of the “WP3 – Design and development of autonomous driving technologies for harsh weather conditions”. Task 3.5 – “Definition of system specification & design of the architecture” uses the overall scope of the targeted System of Systems coming from task 2.1 and the functional requirements related to ADV coming from task 2.4. This leads at defining a functional architecture solution and design concepts to cover functional requirements.

The first part deals with the scope of the current report a brief description of the different targeted platforms and an introduction of the model based-design approach adopted for architecture design.

The second part of this report deals with a more theoretical demarch, it is composed of the chapters three and four.

Third chapter deals with detailed explanation on the concepts that will be used to model the architecture design solution. Then, it abords more precisely how Capella can be used to model the high-level system of systems scoping the AGTS.

The fourth chapter provides details on each sub-component, by specifying its role in the ADS solution (referring the D2.1 deliverable), the data flow transiting it and the functionalities in which it is involved or for which sub-component is the main actor. The report continues dealing with the more practical approach aiming to highlight a concretization-like of the previous theoretical concepts in which all architecture design has been described.

The fifth part consists in providing information on the platform that has been used for tests (baggage tractor from TLD), sensors emplacement, sensors details and their location on the vehicle.

The last chapter deals with the means used to guarantee a protection level high enough to be robust against any malicious actions that could harm the availability, the safety and confidentiality of the vehicle and its usage.

2. Introduction

2.1. Purpose & scope

This report aims to determine the ADS architecture and functionalities that are required and designed within AWARD. ADS internal subfunctions will be described highlighting the relation within its functional architecture. As input for safety analysis performed in task 4.1, the designed ADS architecture, will be enriched by additional safety functional requirements to fulfill in the aim of complying with safety related requirements.

Finally, the result of this report will be an input for testing and validation activities of the functional architecture concepts on the different autonomous driving vehicles during T&V activities.

2.2. Confidentiality

This document is public. The content report aims to be shared for external use, to all the partners of the AWARD consortium and extended to anyone else.

2.3. Related documents

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between the different project deliverables.

Figure 1: Relationships and dependencies between the different AWARD deliverables

1. System scope definition

The system architecture of the ADS is based on the output of AWARD T2.1 where architecture of AGTS has been defined through a System of Systems approach as depicted in [D2.1 Figure 14](#). The terms and the terminology that have been defined in task 2.1 are also used in this document to keep consistency between project documents.

2. Functional requirements

Deliverable D2.4 contains the functional requirements for which a functional solution shall be proposed in D3.5. These requirements are derived from an analysis of the different use cases described in WP6.

4. Functional Safety requirements

Upon the delivery of a first version of the functional architecture defined in T3.5, a safety analysis is performed to derive the functional safety requirements. This analysis leads to the creation of functional safety requirements and/or modification of functional requirements which eventually results in a modification of T3.5 functional architecture to comply with the safety requirements. This analysis is usually performed iteratively after each ADS functional architecture release. The safety methodology is described in D4.1.

2.4. Applicability and target platforms

Baggage tractor (Testing vehicle)

This platform, manufactured by TLD, is the first platform that will be used within AWARD to integrate the AWARD sensors and AWARD ADS to perform data acquisitions and testing activities.

This vehicle is usually used in factories, warehouses, airports to carry trailers embedding goods. Its top speed is around 25 kph and it can operate in complex outdoor/indoor environments and shall be able to interact with doors, barriers, or traffic lights.

Other targeted platforms

The AWARD sensors and ADS will be integrated on all project platforms (Kion, Kamag and Terberg, [figure 2](#)) to tackle the different project use cases.

Figure 2: AWARD autonomous driving vehicle platforms

More information on the platforms and related use cases can be found in chapter 5.4.2 *Vehicle platform* in [D2.1](#) deliverable.

2.5. Model Based-Design approach

As mentioned before, the AGTS is composed of a structure of subsystems interacting with each other. In this configuration called “systems of systems”, the choice of a formalized and reliable approach for modelling the system is decisive and mandatory. MBSE (Model Based-Systems Engineering) is one of the most useful methodologies to break down systems into functional blocks and this modelling approach is used in this deliverable.

One of the most important benefits of this methodology is that MBSE modelling can be started from any classic documents as tables, texts, or images. Moreover, using a MBSE tool allows keeping intellectual consistency within the model and all end users or stakeholders can access the knowledge in a common formalism and shared data base.

Depending on the point of view and role of people accessing the model, interpretation of the content can differ from the designed real content. In next chapter, a brief explanation of concepts will help understand to avoid interrogations.

Within AWARD the Capella open-source tool was used to carry out the MBSE activities.

3. Designing with Capella tool

Capella is a MBSE tool that can be used to define a workflow from stakeholder needs down to the definition of a hardware physical architecture answering the stakeholder needs. The design workflow can be represented at following architecture levels:

- Operational analysis
- System analysis
- Logical architecture
- Physical architecture

The approach can be processed in a top-down (commonly when starting a new project), as well as in a bottom-up way (if the project already exists). Each step can be done independently from one another. For the AWARD project, the previous work packages deliveries already defined a full and complete operational analysis in a textual formalism as well as a system breakdown. Consequently, operational analysis and system modelling will not be performed in Capella and D3.5 will focus on the designing of the logical architecture and its functions.

3.1. Design concepts

3.1.1. Logical Architecture

This represents the design solution independently from any choice of hardware implementation because any logical concept shall depict what is strictly needed.

Definition of the logical architecture forces the modeler to create a logical entity that is required to build the system solution. Using this level of approach to design the AWARD architecture concepts, makes sense to integrate functional requirements. This logical modelling level allows to identify exhaustively all functions that must be integrated in the next modelling step: physical architecture. As an example, if a functional requirement deals with speed adjustments, a logical function must be created to cover it.

3.1.2. Logical Component (LC)

In AWARD, AGTS is the main system derived from the project goals. In Capella, the model element used for representing this single system is the **Logical Component**. As AGTS is a System Of Systems, AGTS LC can be composed of several other LCs. This introduces the notion of parent (container) / children (part) (figure 3).

Figure 3: Logical Component illustration

For example, AGTS contains (is composed of) four main sub-systems LOFM, SLS, SI and ADS. When finishing describing each sub-system as a LC in Capella, this will lead to a full **AGTS**

description (cf. section 3.3.1) with a hierarchy level between them. One LC shall be seen as a not necessarily physical entity. Several physical components can tackle one single LC and several LCs can be addressed by only one single physical component.

3.1.3. Logical Function (LF)

One or several Logical Functions can be owned by a LC. This helps define what a sub-system may do to cover a functional requirement or to participate to the realization of an upper LF owned by the parent LC (figure 4). A LF is distinguished by its name, which specifies the function that is fulfilled. A modeling choice has been taken to prefix each LF name with the LC in charge of realizing the LF. This way of naming enables to always identify which LC is involved.

Figure 4: Logical Function illustration

A LF also can detain one and only one single Function Output Port, which may mean that LF is independent and may only exist because it provides a mandatory information for the system. For example, the box [LC] Independent LF is a function providing specific data thanks to a system “black box” whose internal functional decomposition is unknown (figure 5).

Figure 5: Independent Logical Function illustration

Depending on the goal of a LF, it may detain one/several Function Input or Output Port, through which information transits.

3.1.4. Functional Exchange (FE)

To exchange information between Logical Functions, the notion of Functional Exchanges is needed (figure 6). The transiting information shall concatenate the right level of information to make the functional exchange as clear as possible.

In this report, FEs are named usually with key end words like “data”, “status”, “command” or “set point” because these names fit with the needs derived from the functional architecture target, but their naming is totally arbitrary and decided by the modeler.

Figure 6: Functional Exchange illustration

3.1.5. Diagram (LAB)

To illustrate how LFs owned by LCs exchange information with FEs, **Logical Architecture Blank** diagrams are used. These diagrams are used to tackle main capabilities. For each one identified, a LAB is created in which a functional solution is proposed and for which several scenarios can be imagined. For example, in a same LAB, depending on the interpretation of the value exchanged between two LFs, the functional architecture solution remains valid.

3.1. Physical design concepts

For information, the following introduced concepts are only used in **electrical ADS view** (see [section 8.2 ADV electrical view](#) in annex).

3.1.1. Physical Architecture

This represents the design of the hardware implementation that embody the solution defined in the **logical architecture** proposal. The physical architecture forces the modeler to create concrete electrical components on which can be allocated a **LC** and this level makes sense to visualize the nature of connections binding them. This allows to identify exhaustively all components on which the system will be developed and built.

3.1.2. Physical Component (PC)

In Capella, the model element used for representing a single hardware component is the **Physical Component** in yellow in [figure 7](#).

Figure 7: Logical Component illustration

As an example, the Physical Component ADS PC (in yellow [Figure 43](#) in annex) represents the Logical Component **ADS** embedded in the ADV.

3.1.3. Physical Link

Physical Link is used to materialize the support of the exchanged information between Physical Components. It is represented in red line ([figure 8](#)).

Figure 8: Physical Link illustration

3.2. Co-design with functional requirements

Functional requirements impact and guide directly the design of architecture concepts. These requirements can be imported into Capella and used as a design input. All D2.4 requirements have consequently been imported into Capella. A Capella requirement element is shown in figure 9.

Figure 9: Requirement illustration

Each requirement is imported as a single model element with a unique identifier and other attributes like text of the requirement (figure 10).

Req IF Identifier	AD-OC:OA:AT:PA-U4-01
Req IF Long Name	
Req IF Name	Shall be able to drive in areas with different kinds of restrictions (private/public)
Req IF Prefix	
Req IF Text	The ADV shall be able to recognize the driving area (public/private roads) and ad...

Figure 10: Requirement attributes illustration

The functional requirement model element is then linked to the functional design model element by a relation “#Satisfies” that symbolizes consideration of the requirement in designing approach (figure 11).

Figure 11: Requirement allocation to LF illustration

The link is visual and significates a strong semantic information between both model elements.

3.3. AWARD Design context

3.3.1. AWARD AGTS

Figure 12: Logical architecture view of ADS in context of AGTS

Based on *D2.1 Figure 14* system decomposition, an equivalent diagram was modelled in Capella. *Figure 12* represents the AGTS LC's structure. Each block is a LC and the one that contains all others is the AGTS block. The definition of each logical component doesn't lead to the creation of a n-to-n physical component. At this level of representation, AGTS shall not be seen as a future physical software or hardware component but shall be understood as an entity that must logically exist because it represents the entire solution system. However, ADV platform shall be seen as the future physical vehicle that will be part of the entire ADV logical component. Relationships and flows of information will be detailed later in diagrams dedicated to logical functions realizing an ADV functionality, where functional exchanges are specifically critical to be represented.

This report focuses on the ADV LC that is composed of several entities that shall interact with each other to make ADV capable to drive autonomously. More precisely, the entity in charge of the ADV autonomy is the AWARD ADS, colored in green in *figure 12* and *figure 13*, which can be broken down in other logical components, each one dedicated to a specific function achievement.

Another view of the logical architecture breakdown is the logical component breakdown where the level of components is illustrated (*figure 13*).

This view is useful for the reader to check the component level in the AGTS structure.

3.3.2. AWARD ADV

Zooming into the ADV (part/children of AGTS), enables to see the ADS in the context of the ADV. Only component exchanges within the ADV are shown in [figure 14](#). Names are useful to understand at high level what kind of information is exchanged between each LC. This diagram shows how the connected autonomous driving vehicle is relying on sensors, software or hardware actuators to be able to drive autonomously.

This architecture shows the functional information exchanges, thus connections between LC do not represent hardware connections. As an example, considering the LC EasyMile System, the physical hardware link EM output and EM output to monitor will be common, but in this diagram two connections are depicted to show that the functional information used by ADS-Sense is different from the one used by ADS-Monitor and two data flows are modeled. The first data flow is used in its entirety by ADS-Sense while the other one is used more specifically or partially for monitoring purposes by ADS-Monitor.

Furthermore, alternatively to the autonomous mode, the two [LC Tele operation and Connectivity V2Operator \(figure 14\)](#), are involved to control the vehicle movement through ADS-Act. These components allow a remote operator to take the control of the ADV. The ADV shall also notify its mode to the remote operation system (auto/manual/teleoperation). The Ottopia system solution will use its own sensor set to control the vehicle and perceive the environment, see [section 8.2 ADV electrical view](#) in annex for more details on the sensor technology.

Figure 13: Structure view of ADS in context of AGTS

Figure 14: AWARD ADS in context of ADV

4. AWARD ADS design

In this chapter, the ADS (figure 15) and its subcomponents will be described in detail as well as the main functions that have been identified for the ADV to be able to drive autonomously. The role and functional information that are needed and produced will be defined for each LC.

Figure 15: AWARD ADS and its identified main functions

This chapter adopts a top-down approach by refining main functions. The goal is to determine main functions along with their subfunction's to fulfill the user's needs. The functionalities that will be described in this deliverable have been selected to cover most of task 2.4 functional requirements.

4.1. ADS-Sense

This chapter focuses on the ADS-Sense LC, specifying the incoming and outgoing data flows and detailing its constitutive subfunctions and their relationships.

4.1.1. Role

ADS-Sense LC supports the environmental perception functions using different kind of sensor technologies (radars, lidars, cameras). It also embeds additional sensors to estimate the autonomous vehicle's own position and orientation (GNSS and IMU respectively). The ADS-Sense LC exploits all data provided by the entire sensor-set to fulfill two main keys functions (figure 16).

Figure 16: Functions involving mainly ADS-Sense

Localization: Localize ADV (figure 16)

This functionality is at the core of the autonomous driving software as it allows to estimate the ADV ego position in real time.

Perception: Compute consolidated object list (figure 16)

This functionality is dedicated to obstacle detection, classification, and tracking function. Common obstacles are cars, static objects, or pedestrians, bikes etc. Obstacles are detected by the different sensor modalities and their related data processing software to generate sensor specific obstacle lists. These obstacle lists are then fused within the ADS-Sense to provide a consolidated obstacle list to be further processed by the ADS-Plan LC.

Operational sensing status

This functionality is crucial to evaluate if sensors are operating in their nominal or degraded state, to ensure that their data can be used by localization and/or perception functions. Provide sensors operational status (figure 16) is the identified LF to monitor sensor health status.

4.1.2. Data flow

Figure 17: I/O of ADS-Sense

4.1.2.1. ADS-Sense inputs

All FEs <Sensor company provider> output	Left incoming port , collects all sensor outputs to be further post processed within the ADS-Sense LC.
--	--

4.1.2.2. ADS-Sense outputs

FE Navigation info & FE Navigation info to monitor	Right outgoing port , provides information that has been before processed by sensing algorithms to provide functional outputs for ADS-Plan and ADS-Monitor.
FE Navigation info for remote control	Same outgoing port (figure 17) as the row above, provides video streams transmitted from ADS to teleoperation center.

ADS sense function will be further detailed in the next chapters.

4.1.3. Functions details

4.1.3.1. Localization

Within AWARD, different type of sensor modalities will be used as a localization input. The objective is to take advantage of the heterogeneous sensor types to compensate for each other's weaknesses to improve the reliability and integrity of the ego vehicle position estimation. The different sensor modalities are described in Sensors (ADS-Sense) subsections (see 5.2 Sensors (Inputs for ADS-Sense) page 43).

4.1.3.1.1. Functional explanation

Figure 18: Provide consolidated localization diagram

As shown in figure 18, the number of localization sources, commonly called modalities, were increased within AWARD to improve the localization accuracy, availability, and safety. Indeed, the following modalities will be used:

- Radar based localization (LCs Navtech radar System and Continental radar System).
- Vision based localization (LC EasyMile System) can detect ground markings and borders for contributing to consolidate the position.
- Lidars based localization (LC EasyMile System) build respectively one map per lidar technology.
- Odometry position estimation based on IMU.
- Absolution position estimation based on GNSS corrected with real time kinetic data (RTK).

Radar, vision, and lidar localization functions usually require prior known maps recorded with the respective sensing modality. These maps usually contain fixed static elements such as (ground markings, buildings, posts) depending on the modality.

The GNSS RTK system that will be used on the different platforms withing AWARD is able to reach a centimetric precision and two antennas are usually integrated on the ADVs to estimate the ADV heading.

All modalities are then fused together to provide a consolidate localization output and determine the localization uncertainty. This fused output shall be robust to varying environmental conditions like weather, and also to transitions from indoor to outdoor.

For example, within a Lidar based modality, several maps and consequently localization functions can be determined (figure 19). The generated maps and localization performances for each sensor type will then depend on the sensor characteristics (FOV, range, density, accuracy...) and on its mounting position on the ADV (height, orientation). For example, sensors located close to the ground are likely to be obstructed by parked cars or pedestrian.

Different maps can be acquired using the same acquisition trajectory (in blue in figure 19).

Figure 19: Localization map

- Map in green acquired with lidar (MRS + MCS) modality
- Map in red acquired with lidar (VLP32) modality

MRS and MCS map and VLP32 maps are different as MRS and MCS are integrated close to the ground and have a range around 20 m, whereas VLP32 is on the ADV roof and has a 150 m range. In both cases, maps are manually processed to remove non static objects or ground detections.

Both ADS-Sense and ADS-Monitor spy the fused localization to verify that all modality sources are consistent with one another. If too many modalities diverge from each other or if monitoring detects that too many modalities as being in default, a vehicle safe state request is triggered as the localization function is not considered to be reliable anymore, which could cause a safety issue.

Testing activities will show how the localization function can be improved by the AWARD sensor systems to be robust to adverse weather conditions.

4.1.3.2. Perception

4.1.3.2.1. Functional explanation

Lidars, radars, thermal and vision cameras are used to detect the various obstacles and provide this information to the ADS-Sense in the form of an object list having its attributes depending on the sensor type used during the acquisition of data. ADS-Sense then aggregates the different obstacle lists to build a fused obstacle list. The objective of using several independent sensor modalities is to increase the redundancy, reliability, and robustness to adverse weather conditions (figure 20).

Figure 20: Sensor's LFs involved in perception function

As an example, lidars obstacle detection performance is usually degraded by fog and rain whereas radars or thermal imaging systems shall be more immune to this weather conditions. Using multiple sensors modalities enables to compensate the weaknesses of one sensor technology with the other sensor technologies and being able to deliver the intended obstacle detection function.

4.1.3.3. Sensor operational status

4.1.3.3.1. Functional explanation

According to each sensor internal status assessment, a consolidated sensor-set status is computed by the ADS-Sense LC (figure 21). The failure root cause can come from a sensor that is damaged, faulty or a sensor FOV obstruction detection that degrades its perception capabilities. The knowledge of the sensor status can allow the ADS-Sense to disregard the sensor data and eventually trigger a "degraded" mode configuration in the ADS-Plan.

Figure 21: Provide sensors operational status diagram

4.2. ADS-Plan

This chapter aims to determine what ADS-Plan takes as an input to determine the navigation planification task and focus on incoming and outgoing data flows that will be detailed.

4.2.1. Role

This sub-system gathers **ADS-Sense** information but also data coming from semantic maps, LOFM or other constraints. ADS-Plan shall determine the optimal motion planning. The high-level ADS function Plan ADV dynamic driving actions can be split into three main sub-functions that ADV realizes:

- Avoid a collision with obstacles.
- Follow a predefined trajectory stored in a map.
- Cross an intersection equipped with a connected traffic light.

To fulfill these subfunctions some generic LFs (and common LFs coming from ADS-Sense or ADS-Act) are used and, according to the functional need, ADS-Plan must, for example:

- Predict objects movement to avoid a collision.
- Determine speed and steering set points to follow a trajectory.
- Read dedicated elements from semantic maps to cross an intersection with a traffic light.

ADS-Plan is also mainly involved for determining if the ADV is operational or not according to the others subcomponent operational status (figure 22).

Figure 22: Functions involving mainly ADS-Plan

Nominally, the ADS-Plan works with a predefined trajectory and maximum speed limit along this trajectory or subsets of the trajectory. Other parameters can also be configured along the

trajectory and are used by the motion planning algorithm. Notable events like traffic lights, intersections, right priorities are also added on the map and their position is preset on the ADV trajectory to trigger a specific behavior.

A specific diagram for each functionality is detailed in the following section.

4.2.2. Data flow

Figure 23: I/O of ADS-Plan

4.2.2.1. ADS-Plan inputs

FE Navigation info	The left incoming port (figure 23) collects ADS-Sense object list & localization information, then processes it to plan which action the vehicle must do according to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – what the ADV detects, – where the ADV is planning to go, – where the objects are planning to go, – where the ADV is localized on the map.
FE Navigation fbk	The ADS-Plan also requires navigation feedbacks to estimate the real time state of the vehicle. The right incoming port (Figure 23) enables to assess platform health signs and aims to determine if the platform is still operational or not.

4.2.2.2. ADS-Plan outputs

FE Navigation plan	Consuming the ADS-Sense information, and with the help of other data stored externally, ADS-Plan determines through its right outgoing port (figure 23), navigation commands that the ego AV shall follow. Then, this navigation plan is sent to ADS-Act that consumes it to manage the relevant actuators.
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4.2.3. Functions details

4.2.3.1. Provide stored site map

4.2.3.1.1. Functional explanation

Access to the stored site map is mandatory for almost all functions fulfilled by ADS-Plan. These maps embed the knowledge on trajectories to follow during a mission or on road restrictions on a trajectory or other navigation relevant parameters.

4.2.3.2. Collision Avoidance

This function objective is to avoid collisions with obstacles by reducing the ADV speed, no evasive maneuvers are considered thus the ADV can only brake along its predefined path. In the current implementation it is important to understand that ADS-Plan sends steering

commands to follow the predefined trajectory and speed commands to react to the presence of obstacles.

4.2.3.2.1. Functional explanation

The collision avoidance functionality requires three inputs (figure 24):

- The map with its accessible semantic elements like navigable lanes, intersections, parameters along the trajectory.
- The detected obstacle list.
- The current ADV localization.

Figure 24: AWARD Collision Avoidance

The following subfunctions are part of the ADS-Plan LC.

4.2.3.2.1.1. Predict obstacle movement

To predict obstacle movement the ADV shall know the position of detected obstacles relative to its position, their speed, the surrounding navigable roads, and the road connection. These information are then used to determine a collision risk and thus adapt the ADV speed.

If the perception of the environment is degraded, the LF Localize ADV and Compute consolidated obstacle list coming from the left in figure 24 shall take advantage of the different sensing modalities they are made of to compensate the degraded sensing performances. In the worst case, the ADS-Sense function failure will trigger a degraded mode request or trigger an ADV safe stop.

The FE Semantic map outgoing from LF Provide stored site map, represents semantic elements that are contained in the map; an example is shown in figure 25.

Figure 25: Semantic map used for prediction

- Manual acquisition in blue
- Superposition of ego ADV navigable lane related to each edge of the trajectory
- Orange paths colored according to their radius of curvature

4.2.3.2.1.2. Evaluate collision risk with obstacles

To evaluate a collision risk, ADS shall compute its future trajectory and estimate the future trajectory of adverse obstacles. In case the trajectories are likely to intersect each other this function will output a speed setpoint to avoid the collision.

4.2.3.2.1.3. Compute optimal speed command

ADS-Plan will get speed setpoints from various subfunctions. This function will take the lowest speed request which is limiting and forward it to the ADS-Act subcomponent. Other speed setpoints can be requested by localization uncertainty monitoring function or by lateral acceleration monitoring function for example.

4.2.3.3. Trajectory following

This function details how ADS can follow its predefined trajectory.

4.2.3.3.1. Functional explanation

Following a trajectory requires the follow LC and related LF (figure 26):

- ADS-Sense to enable positioning.
- ADS-Plan to enable speed and steering adjustments.
- ADS-Act to ensure speed and steering commands are transferred to the platform and collect feedbacks from the platform.
- ADS-Monitor to monitor trajectory deviations.

Figure 26: AWARD trajectory following

As shown in figure 26, the trajectory following function can be decomposed in the following subfunctions.

As detailed in [Localize ADV](#), ADS-Sense provides a robust position available and processable by both ADS-Plan and ADS-Monitor independently from each other.

First, ADS-Plan Determine commands to follow a predefined trajectory thanks to the stored trajectory and by localizing ADV position on it. Then, navigation orders can be computed according to the current speed and steering values given by the platform. The aim is to determine the speed to reach and the steering to apply to fit the predefined trajectory.

In parallel, a continuous trajectory deviation detection is computed by ADS-Monitor to [detect if the ADV will](#) deviate from the intended trajectory.

4.2.3.4. Crossing intersections with traffic lights

In the next chapter, the ADV behavior when crossing an intersection with traffic light in autonomous mode will be described.

4.2.3.4.1. Functional explanation

To achieve intersection crossing with traffic light, the localization information from ADS-S is required as well as information from the map, and also from the traffic light itself. Indeed, we assume the traffic light from LC Supporting Infrastructure (SI) is connected and can at least provide its phase (color) and the remaining time before phase switch ([figure 27](#)).

Figure 27: Crossing intersections with traffic lights

The traffic light status exchanged between SI and ADV relies on a V2X communication. The signal status (signal phase) and the remaining time are used to determine the speed setpoint to be communicated to the ADS-Plan for further processing. This speed setpoint is communicated by Determine ADV speed according to traffic light status.

The traffic light position is known by the ADS Plan as set in the predefined map along with the traffic light stop position (figure 28).

Figure 28: Semantic traffic light element on path

In case the ADV is not able to communicate with the traffic light, it will stop at the predefined stop position, despite the traffic light color.

In parallel, ADS-Monitor also makes a monitoring on the traffic light status (Signal phase shown in Figure 27) and uses as input the consolidated localization (Current position shown in Figure 27). See section 4.4.3.3 Safe monitoring in approach of traffic light intersection for more details.

4.3. ADS-Act

This chapter aims at determining the input/output used or generated by the ADS-Act LC to fulfill its subfunctions.

4.3.1. Role

ADS-Act translates high level planification commands into platform understandable commands. As it is said in D2.1, ADS-Act will perform the platform control (Perform platform control in figure 29) by knowing the navigation set point and being in charge of actuator control (propulsion, steering and braking systems).

Figure 29: Functions involving mainly ADS-Act

ADS Act is also in charge of the vehicle accessories control such as low/high beams, automated platform systems, horn, etc. ADS-Act will also handle safe state requests provided by the ADS-Plan or ADS-Monitor LC (Figure 30).

4.3.2. Data flow

Figure 30: I/O of ADS-Act

ADS-Act ideally may be a role-gateway like, formatting navigation requests coming from FE Navigation plan and/or FE Safety navigation cmd into interpretable commands for the platform, then formatting platform information (FE Platform info) into interpretable feedbacks for navigation.

4.3.2.1. ADS-Act inputs

FE Navigation plan & FE Safety navigation cmd	In figure 30 , both, left incoming port , collect respectively FEs related to the navigation plan and to the safety monitoring command to translate them into driving commands.
FE Platform info	ADS-Act requires to know the platform information (containing a platform status) to be able to evaluate an instantaneous state of the vehicle. This aims at determining if the ego AV is still ready and operational for applying driving commands.

4.3.2.2. ADS-Act outputs

FE Driving cmd	Driving commands are computed and provided to ADV-Platform sub-component through the right outgoing port in figure 30 . According to received safety commands, either only an optimal speed / steering is needed, either a stop is engaged because a danger has been detected by ADS-Monitor (detailed below).
FE Navigation fbk	According to platform information, the operational vehicle state along with measured feedbacks are provided to ADS-Plan and ADS-Monitor across the left outgoing port .

4.3.2.3. ADS-Act Inputs/outputs

FE Teleop request + Act fbck	In this case, teleoperation control has been activated after requesting the FMS to deactivate all autonomous functions. Once activated and according to the Otopia camera system feedback, the remote-control commands are directly applied on the ADV platform. This FE ensures to provide the remote driving commands to ADV-Platform and allows ADV-Platform to expose its state through the in out port in figure 30 .
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4.3.3. Functions details

4.3.3.1. Interaction with road users

This function aims to show how the ADV can interact with other road users to be able to ease the understanding of the ADV driving intentions or state.

The FEs Activable accessory and Trajectory to follow outgoings from LF Provide stored site map, enables ADS-Plan to determine which accessories to activate along the predefined ADV trajectory ([figure 31](#)). The accessories can also be activated directly by the ADS Plan, for example, when following a slow-moving obstacle, the ADS Plan can decide to activate the buzzer through the Forward accessory command to platform function.

4.3.3.1.1. Functional explanation

Figure 31: AWARD Interacting with road users

4.4. ADS-Monitor

This chapter aims at defining the incoming/outgoing data flow from the ADS-Monitor LC and identify its subfunctions.

ADS-Monitor is a safety backup system which triggers safe state requests that preempts the nominal navigation commands. This system is designed to be triggered in case of ADS-Plan failure.

4.4.1. Role

This is an additional AGTS sub-component which is introduced by the architecture design solution to tackle the functional safety concepts. This system consists in realizing the main monitoring actions that are required to cover most of the functional safety requirements.

The main ADS-Monitor output is a safe state request from Trigger safe state request (figure 32), that symbolizes a command to force the ADV to a safe state which is a full AV stop. The safe state request is a command allowing to use a higher deceleration value with respect to the one nominally used by ADS-Plan to stop the ADV.

Figure 32: Functions involving mainly ADS-Monitor

4.4.2. Data flow

Figure 33: I/O of ADS-Monitor

4.4.2.1. ADS-Monitor inputs

FE Sensor & Navigation info to monitor	In figure 33, the left incoming port , collects sensor and navigation information for which integrity shall be monitored.
FE EM output to monitor	Specific sensor data is also use by the ADS-Monitor to implement an emergency anti-collision function.
FE Navigation fbk to monitor	The right incoming port , is used by ADS-Monitor to acquire platform feedbacks used by its subfunctions.

4.4.2.2. ADS- Monitor outputs

FE Safety cmd	The safe state requests are provided to ADS-Act sub-component through the right outgoing port .
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4.4.3. Functions details

4.4.3.1. Emergency collision avoidance

Figure 34: Monitoring for collision avoidance

In parallel to the collision avoidance function done by the ADS-Plan (cf. section 4.2.3.2 Collision Avoidance), a monitoring of an emergency anticollision area is performed by the ADS-Monitor (figure 34). This area is computed considering the FEs related to the current steering angle feedback and the current speed feedback along with ADV dynamic and geometrical parameters. Additionally, ADS Monitor uses raw lidars data to detect if an obstacle is in the computed ADV emergency collision area to trigger a safe state request if needed.

ADS Plan anticollision and ADS Monitor emergency collision avoidance functions are independent.

4.4.3.2. Trajectory deviation detection

Figure 35: Monitoring for trajectory deviation

In parallel to the ADS-Plan trajectory following function (cf. section 4.2.3.3 [Trajectory following](#)), a trajectory deviation monitoring function is continuously performed by ADS-Monitor (figure 35). This monitoring relies on the current speed feedback, the current steering angle feedback, and the geometrical vehicle parameters (through several dedicated FEs) to project the future trajectory of the vehicle and assess if the projected trajectory exits the allowed navigable lane. In case of trajectory deviation detection, a safe state request is triggered to stop the ADV.

4.4.3.3. Safe monitoring in approach of traffic light intersection

Figure 36: Monitoring for traffic light intersections

As mentioned in section 4.2.3.4 [Crossing intersections with traffic lights](#), to safely cross an intersection handled by a traffic light, a robust localization information, and also information from the traffic light have to be transmitted with a given level of integrity (position and phase/timing/traffic light ID). Therefore, the ADS-Monitor also assesses if the communication with the traffic light is suitable for safe operations.

The ADS monitor can trigger a safe state request whenever the ADS-Plan does not act properly and if the ADV is about to run a red light.

4.4.3.4. Functional safety requirements

The functional architecture is then used for further safety analysis which aim at assigning safety level on each safety critical function. This analysis is done within D4.1 and some of the safety requirements are illustrated in [table 1](#).

Table 1: Allocated requirements to safety functions

Topic	Text	ASIL	Allocation
Collision Avoidance	Provide radar object list & attributes	A(C)	Continental radar System
	Provide vision object list & attributes	A(C)	Foresight vision System
	Provide thermal vision object list & attributes	A(C)	Adasky camera
	Provide object list & attributes	A(C)	Easymile System
	Provide raw lidar data	B(C)	
	Compute consolidated object list	A(C)	ADS Sense
	Localize ADV	A(C)	
	Predict obstacle movement	A(C)	ADS Plan
	Evaluate collision risk with obstacle	A(C)	
	Compute optimal speed command	A(C)	
	Evaluate collision risk with obstacle	B(C)	ADS Monitor
	Trigger safe state request	B(C)	
	Get steering feedback	B(C)	ADS Act
	Get speed feedback	C(C)	
	Forward speed command to platform	A(C)	
	Decide to forward safe state request	B(C)	
	Apply requested speed command	C(C)	ADV platform
	Provide speed feedback	C(C)	
Provide steering feedback	B(C)		
Trajectory deviation detection	Provide stored site map	D(D)	ADS
	Localize ADV	D(D)	ADS Sense
	Determine commands to follow predefined trajectory	A(D)	ADS Plan
	Compute optimal steering command	A(D)	
	Compute optimal speed command	A(D)	
	Project the AV trajectory	C(D)	ADS Monitor
	Trigger safe state request	C(D)	
	Get steering feedback	C(D)	ADS Act
	Get speed feedback	C(D)	
	Forward speed and steering command to platform	A(D)	

Topic	Text	ASIL	Allocation
	Decide to forward safe state request	C(D)	ADV platform
	Apply requested steering command	A(D)	
	Apply requested speed command	C(D)	
	Provide speed feedback	D(D)	
	Provide steering feedback	D(D)	
Crossing intersections with traffic lights	Provide stored site map	D(D)	ADS
	Localize ADV	D(D)	ADS Sense
	[RSU] Provide current status of traffic light	D(D)	SI
	Determine AV speed according traffic light status	A(D)	ADS Plan
	Monitor AV speed according traffic light status	C(D)	ADS Monitor
	Trigger safe state request	C(D)	
	Forward speed command to platform	A(D)	ADS Act
	Decide to forward safe state request	C(D)	
	Apply requested speed command	D(D)	ADV platform
	Provide speed feedback	A(D)	

4.5. System integrity errors

Errors shall be monitored in all logical components and their related subfunctions and shall allow the ADS Plan component to decide if the ADV can be autonomously operated.

4.5.1. Role

The role of this function is to continuously verify the integrity of the entire system.

4.5.2. Functional explanation

Figure 37: Consolidate AV status and errors

The LF Consolidate ADV status for FMS takes as inputs a set of errors that ADS may face (figure 37). These errors can come from different sources, as software as hardware. These errors are interpreted by the ADS-Plan and then forwarded to the LOFM for further high level planification activities. All safety critical components are monitored by the ADS-Monitor LC and a safe state triggered in case of an error detection and the error root cause is provide to ADS-Plan for further action.

4.5.2.1. Provide sensors operational status

According to each sensor status, a consolidated sensor-set status is provided by the ADS-Sense. Sensor failure origin can have multiple root causes, such as out of range temperature, over/under voltage or a detected sensor obstruction that prevents a full capacity of use (figure 38).

Figure 38: Provide sensors operational status

This sensor status consolidation is then used by the ADS-Plan to decide whether autonomous mode is possible and if a degraded mode shall be used.

4.5.2.2. Provide platform status

The current state of the platform is another source of information for consolidating the ADV status before informing the LOFM. The function in charge to build this information is called Provide platform status (figure 39). This function aims at determining a platform functional state depending on the status of its subcomponents. This information can be further used by LOFM to send a maintenance team of removing the ADV from the operational activities for example.

Figure 39: Provide platform status

4.5.2.3. Fuse and aggregate ADV errors

ADV platform and ADS-Monitor information are being pushed to ADS-Plan by ADS-Act considering the current implementation.

5. Sensors & ADS integration

This chapter aims to highlight the practical implementation of the previously described architecture on a first tests vehicle.

5.1. Testing vehicle (ADV)

Figure 40: Baggage tractor outdoor by day and by night

A TLD vehicle was used for the first testing activities and embedded all project sensors. This vehicle with its sensors is shown in figure 40. This vehicle also has the communication capacities with LOFM, SI, SLS and road users.

5.2. Sensors (Inputs for ADS-Sense)

5.2.1. Radars

Two different types of radars are embedded in the ADV.

5.2.1.1. Terran360 from Navtech

Table 2: Navtech radar datasheet details

	CAS Ph1	CAS Ph2
IP Rating / IK rating	IP67	IP67
Operating temperature	-20°C +70°C	-40°C +70°C
Able to detect field of view occlusions?	No (not difficult to implement if required) No issue with occlusions in field testing radar	No (not difficult to implement if required) No issue with occlusions in field testing radar
Able to detect sensor errors?	Health Measurements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rotation Rate - Packet Rate - Temperature - RF Health - Motor current 	Health Measurements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rotation Rate - Packet Rate - Temperature - RF Health - Motor current
Operating Frequency	76-77 GHz	76-77 GHz

	CAS Ph1	CAS Ph2
Instrumented Range	120 m 270 m	120 m 270 m
Range Resolution	0.04 m 0.175 m	0.04 m 0.175 m
Azimuth Beamwidth	3.6 Degree	3.6 Degree
Elevation Beamwidth	3.6 Degree	3.6 Degree
Field of View	360 Degree	360 Degree
Measurement Rate	400 per rotation	400 per rotation
Update Rate	4/8/10Hz	4/8/10Hz
Time Synchronisation	NTP	NTP/PTP
Data Connection	1 Gbps Ethernet	1 Gbps Ethernet
Power Consumption	24 Watts	24 Watts
Power Supply	24 Volt DC	PoE
Weight	6 kg	4 kg
Height	250 mm	250 mm
Diameter	270 mm	160 mm
Connectors	Power – M12 X Code Data – M12 X Code	PoE – M12 X Code

Table 3: Roof radar usage and position

Navtech	Sensor integration details
	<p>This sensor is a rotating radar with a 360° field of view of the environment. The radar frequency can be tuned from 3 Hz to 10 Hz depending on the intended application as the range is lowered when increasing the frequency (3XX m to 2XX m).</p> <p>For AWARD this radar was mounted on the roof of the TLD platform and raised at the highest position available. This radar will be mostly used to feed a localization function taking advantage of the sensor long perception range. This mechanical integration allows static object detection (like buildings, walls, poles...) while limiting field of view obstruction by parked cars or trailers.</p>

5.2.1.2. Continental SRS 520 System with 6 RADARS around the vehicle

Table 4: Radars belt datasheet details

	Far Scan	Near Scan
IP Rating / IK rating	IP6K9K + IPx6K + IPx7	

	Far Scan	Near Scan
Operating temperature	-40°C to + 85°C	
Able to detect field of view occlusions?	Yes	
Able to detect sensor errors?	Yes	
Operating range	100 m	13 m
Range accuracy	0.63 m	0.20 m
FoV Azimuth	+/- 75°	
Speed Range	+/- 300 kph	
Speed resolution	0.34 kph	1.18 kph
Weight	~ 145 g	

Table 5: Vehicle belt radar usage and position

Continental	Sensor integration details
	<p>The six radars are integrated around the TLD vehicle at different positions to fully perceive the AV surroundings. The range of these radars for pedestrian and motorized vehicles is ~100m.</p> <p>The system provided by Continental embeds a centralized tracking system outputting a list of obstacles with attributes that can be used for obstacle detection and the ADV absolute position for localization.</p>

5.2.2. Cameras

5.2.2.1. Adasky viper Thermal imaging system

Table 6: Adasky viper camera datasheet details

	Sensor characteristics values
IP Rating / IK rating	IP67, IP69K on front lens
Operating temperature	-40°C to + 85°C
Able to detect field of view occlusions?	NC
Able to detect sensor errors?	NC
Other important characteristics...	NC

Table 7: Front viper camera usage and position

Adasky	Sensor integration details
	<p>The Adasky thermal camera is located at the top front center of the TLD vehicle and is slightly pitched.</p> <p>The thermal camera works by measuring emissivity the environment. The technology used by this camera relies on both emissivity reflectance of an object and deep learning algorithms to distinguish cars, pedestrians, bicycles in the image.</p> <p>This camera shall improve the obstacle detection performances especially during bad lightning conditions or in foggy/rainy situations.</p>

5.2.2.2. Foresight multi spectral stereoscopic imaging system

Table 8: Foresight camera datasheet details

	Sensor characteristics values
IP Rating / IK rating	IP67 / NC
Operating temperature	-20°C to +60°C
Able to detect field of view occlusions?	Yes
Able to detect sensor errors?	Yes

Table 9: Front vision camera usage and position

Foresight	Sensor integration details
	<p>The camera system is localized at the front of the vehicle at 1,20 m of height and at the center of the TLD front panel.</p> <p>This system provides a list of objects. This camera is expected to obstacle detection performances especially under adverse weather conditions like fog, rain, or snow.</p>

5.2.2.3. Ottopia camera (*6)

Table 10: Ottopia camera datasheet details

	Sensor characteristics values
IP Rating / IK rating	IP67 / NC
Operating temperature	-40°C to +85°C
Able to detect field of view occlusions?	NC
Able to detect sensor errors?	NC
Field of view (Horizontal)	108±3°
Field of view (Vertical)	92±3°

Table 11: Ottopia camera usage and position

Ottopia	Sensor integration details
<p>There is not available pictures of the Ottopia cameras because they have not been installed on the testing vehicle concerned in scope of this report.</p>	<p>The number of cameras recommended by the Ottopia teleoperation system must be of 6:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 Front camera positioned at the ADV's centerline. - 1 Rear camera positioned at the ADV's centerline. - 2 mirror cameras (Left and Right) - 2 side cameras (Left and Right)

5.2.3. EasyMile lidar based system

Four lidars are embedded on the TLD vehicle. Two Velodyne multilayer lidars are located at the front top of the vehicle near the Adasky thermal camera while the other two are located at the bottom side corners of the vehicle front.

Table 12: Lidar characteristics

	80-VLP-16-A (Velodyne)	80-VLP-32C-A (Velodyne)	microScan3 (SICK)	MRS1000 (SICK)
Channels	16	32	8	4
IP Rating	IP67			IP 65 / IP 67
Operating temperature	-10°C to +60°C	-20°C to +60°C	-10°C to 50°C	-20°C to +60°C
Operating range	100m	120m	4 m	0.2 m to 64 m
Range accuracy	Up to ±3 cm			
Field of view (Horizontal)	NC	360°	275°	275°
Field of view (Vertical)	30° (+15.0° to - 15.0°)	40° (-25° to +15°)	NC	7.5°
Weight	~ 830 g	~ 925 g	1,15 kg	1.2 kg
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IP65 → According NEMA, 6 significates that sensor is effective against dust tight & 5 significates sensor protection against water jets. - IP67 → According NEMA, 6 significates that sensor is effective against dust tight & 7 significates sensor protection against immersion up to 1 m depth. 				

Table 13: Lidars usage and position

EasyMile	Sensor integration details
	<p>VLP16 and VLP32 lidars are rotating lidars with 16 or 32 layers respectively, the usable range of the VLP16 is around 50 m while the range of the VLP32 is around 150 m.</p> <p>The data from these lidars is mainly used by obstacle detection function or by localization function.</p>
	<p>Lateral lidars, MRS (right) or MCS (left) from SICK, are located at the bottom corners of the vehicle and are used for small object detection and their data is the input of the ADS Monitor LC. These lidars are protected with covers to limit perturbations due to water splashes especially when driving under rain or snow.</p>

5.2.4. Other sensors

5.2.4.1. IMU

The inertial measurement unit is embedded within the EasyMile system. This sensor is used for determining the vehicle orientation in space and is consequently used as an input of the EasyMile [localization](#) and [obstacle detection](#) functions.

Table 14: Embedded IMU model

Component	Model	Brand
SENSOR, IMU	MTI-10-2A8G4	XSENS

5.2.4.2. GNSS

The global navigation satellite system is also embedded in the EasyMile system and used for localization purposes. GNSS is further improved with real time kinetic corrections to reach a centimeter accuracy instead of meter accuracy when using conventional GNSS.

Table 15: Embedded GNSS modem model

Component	Model	Brand
MODEM GNSS	FDDRZNTBN	NOVATEL

5.3. Accessories of the considered test platform (ADV platform)

The TLD test vehicle is capable of interacting and warning other road users when operating a mission through its blinkers, sounds alarms and lights (Figure 41).

Figure 41: Accessories.

Note:

- Positioning lights (1, 2 & 3) and rear reflective lights (4) enable to make the vehicle perceivable by other road users.

- *Buzzers generate sound in a frequency range of 1 to 7 kHz as an audio indication.*
- *Mode lights (3) are activated to evidence the current mode (autonomous = green blinking).*
- *When manually reversing gear simultaneous rear orange lights (3) and buzzer warning are activated.*

These accessories are usually normalized and follow industrial standards that must be respected to ensure security of the vehicle and its environment.

6. Cyber security

6.1. Purpose

The cyber security aims at protecting the vehicle from any potential threats that could come externally to or internally into the vehicle. A threat can be physical or intangible.

6.2. Standards and Best Practices

International standards for autonomous vehicle security are not yet available, as this domain is relatively new. Therefore, we strongly inspired our best practices of Standard SAE J3061, which defines the Cybersecurity Guidebook for Cyber-Physical Vehicle Systems. These best practices cover organizational and technical aspects of vehicle cybersecurity, including governance, risk management, security by design, threat detection, incident response and recovery. Government agencies, cybersecurity experts and security research communities work together to maintain and advance cybersecurity capabilities. This aims at implementing the ISO/SAE 21434, "Road Vehicles – Cybersecurity Engineering" recently released.

6.3. Automated Vehicle (AV)

6.3.1. Overall cybersecurity management

Cybersecurity management processes must be described for each vehicle type, as different management processes could be required for specific vehicles.

6.3.2. Physical Entry Points

The ethernet plug only grants access to authenticated maintenance services. Access to unauthenticated resources like the sensors and the vehicle Internet connection requires the use of an OpenVPN tunnel between the client machine and the vehicle computers. This prevents opportunistic attacks and man-in-the-middle attacks.

6.3.3. Internet connectivity

As a rule, the sensors and accessories can only communicate with a static list of opened ports on selected computers. They cannot communicate with each other, and they cannot go on the internet.

Once provisioned, the vehicle Internet access is protected by an IPSec tunnel with mutual certificate authentication. Before the provisioning, only HTTPS and DNS streams are opened to allow the provisioning. This mitigates malicious traffic interception and GPS correction spoofing on the radio link.

Communications between the vehicle and the control center (Fleet Management System) are protected by a mutually authenticated TLS layer in addition to the IPSec tunnel.

Only the GPS has access to the Internet to get its corrections. All other attempts to access the Internet from equipment are dropped. This mitigates the impact of possible remote exploitation of vulnerabilities in the sensors.

The modem is on a physically isolated network. Additionally, all traffic initiated from this network is unconditionally dropped. This mitigates the impact of a corrupted modem or radio firmware in the modem on the vehicle.

6.3.4. GPS / Localization

The localization algorithm fuses the input from multiple sensors. This brings redundancy and robustness and mitigates GPS signal spoofing.

6.3.5. Obstacle detection

The obstacle detection safety stack is running in an independent loop with redundant sensors. In the unlikely event where an attacker would have gained access to the AWARD ADS PC, the vehicle would remain safe from accidents since the safety chain, independent from ADS PC, will trigger a safe state request upon obstacle detection.

6.3.6. Network

Each computer runs a firewall. This firewall is configured to only allow whitelisted streams from sensors. No sensor has full access to a computer. This mitigates the impact of misbehaving or malicious sensors on computers.

The network switches are configured to isolate the communication between criticality levels (typically safety sensors and other sensors) and prevent any communication between an equipment to another unless explicitly whitelisted. This mitigates the impact of misbehaving or malicious sensors on other equipment. All communications between computers are encapsulated in a VPN connection (except for SSH protocol that is considered strong enough) to ensure confidentiality and integrity of data transmitted.

6.3.7. Sensors

In addition to the maintenance ethernet plug protected by a VPN, all equipment supporting authentication have dedicated passwords. This mitigates direct attacks on sensors. V2X protocol used for communication between RSU and OBU is based on messages signed with public key certificates, ensuring the authentication and integrity of information. Certificate architectures are specifically designed for V2X, for example with a very limited validity.

6.3.8. AWARD ADS solution

The AWARD Ads PC is the machine exposing the API and in charge of all access control. All streams to or from the Internet are routed through this "navigation" computer. The vehicle Operating System is tailor made and mostly built from sources. It is based on the industry standard "Yocto" framework. This allows fine grain control over included components as well as a reduced attack surface.

UEFI anchored Secure Boot is automatically configured and enabled with a unique key on each

machine on the first boot. The secure boot covers all steps from power-on to full install image signature validation. This mitigates offline attacks on the code and guarantees the code has not been altered by a faulty hard drive.

Each computer takes a cryptographic signature of the other computers on the first boot. Further communication with other machines will only proceed if the signature did not change. This is then used to establish an IPSec tunnel between machines to protect robotic communications. This mitigates Man-In-The-Middle attacks between the computers.

Serial and console interfaces are disabled. Computer control can only go through SSH, HTTPS or the control panel.

Internally, most services including maintenance and robotic services run under dedicated users. Only the strict minimal runs as root. Furthermore, the "root" account is fully disabled on production vehicles so that even employees cannot connect as "root" on production vehicles. This mitigates the risks of malicious employees or accidental modification of the system. Software changes including upgrades require physical access to the vehicle and cryptographic signature validation.

As a part of the safety chain, ADS-Monitor provides an important layer to prevent any collision. This solution runs on redundant sensors and can avoid obstacles in the unlikely event of ADS-Plan failure or manual operations. The safety solution itself is redundant with two CPUs working at the same time and monitoring each other. Ethernet and CAN are the main communications support used.

6.3.9. Platform control

Platform control implement mechanism that periodically checks the status of main components connected on the CAN network. These "Keep alive" messages ensure that missing or stolen elements will be detected, and the vehicle will trigger an emergency stop.

Traction, steering, or wheel sensors are redundant to limit the risk of compromised/missing elements (in addition to the safety related requirements).

7. Conclusion

The ADS architecture design has been managed across a methodological approach based on UML formalisms and specific modeling tool which enabled to merge the input requirements and the solution proposal in a common data base of work. The proposed solution is based on the sub systems decomposition proposed in D2.1 and identifies the main functionalities covering functional requirements.

The designed ADS solution relies on the AWARD sensor-set which aims to extend the ego AV sensing capabilities in harsh weather conditions. First, localization function enhancements will be proposed to improve availability and accuracy through an increase of the localization modality number. Second, improvements on obstacle detection function will increase detection performances in adverse weather conditions improving the function availability. Both functions are part of the [ADS-Sense](#) subcomponent described in D2.1.

Consequently, these improvements will improve the performances of the collision avoidance or the trajectory following functions. These functions are further described in the chapter dedicated to [ADS-Plan](#) which depends on ADS-Sense's outputs data to compute its best navigation plan. Platform actuators are controlled through [ADS-Act](#), which translate ADS-Plan planification commands into platform understandable commands. As an alternative to planification commands by ADS-Plan, the Fleet management activates the teleoperation system to remotely intervene on one or several platforms to handle operational situations of the ADV's ODD.

In parallel, the ADS embeds an additional monitoring component to host safety critical functions. A safety analysis of the AWARD ADS architecture has been performed in D4.1 to identify risks and how to mitigate them to reach the expected functional safety level.

The proposes architecture is generic for all platforms and will be used to tackle the different use cases described in D2.1.

8. Annex

8.1. ADV connectivity

Figure 42 illustrates at high level how AWARD ADS can receive missions and continuously provides its status to LOFM. As it deals with functions out of the internal ADS boundaries, this diagram is not depicted in detail but used as an annex to complete the coverage of some specific functional requirements.

Figure 42: ADV connection functions

The role of the LC Connectivity V2Super is to basically broadcast the AV mission APIs for autonomous tasks. This available API provides access to the AV telemetry at 2Hz toward the Fleet Management System and the AV status consolidated by the AWARD ADS. Thanks to these received information, LOFM can Compute optimal mission.

8.2. ADV electrical view

This view relies on the elements described in section 3.1 Design concepts. The scope of this view targets the ADS physical architecture depicting main hardware elements including communication and power supplies network.

Table 16: Physical and Logical allocation (Figure 43)

Physical	Logical
ADS PC	ADS (<u>ADS-Sense</u> & <u>ADS-Plan</u>)
Platform ECU	<u>ADS-Act</u>
Safety ECU	<u>ADS-Monitor</u>
Navtech Radar * 1 + PC	Navtech radar System
Conti Radar * 6 + camera *4 + converter + PC	Continental radar System
Adasky Camera * 1 + PC	Adasky camera System
Foresight Camera * 1 + PC	Foresight vision System
Ottopia Camera * 6 + LTE*4 + GPS + ECU Serial power box + SMA / USB converter + PC Ottopia + Switch Ottopia	Ottopia System
IMU + 4G Modem + Camera + Lidar VLP16 + Lidar VLP32 + Lidar MCS + Lidar MRS	Easymile System
OBU, GNSS Modem	Connectivity
Speed coders + Steering coders + Power boxes	ADV platform

Figure 43: ADV physical view